

Deployment and Experimentation of the Entity Title Architecture at OFELIA Testbed: Learned Lessons Revealed

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Abstract. *Usually the published material about a research project presents the technical challenges, the work conducted and the results from the technical point of view. This work reveals the learned lessons during our participation at the OFELIA project. This different perspective provided from the research contributes with the community by presenting the key success factors which enabled the achievement of the proposed objectives and other important outcomes.*

1. Introduction

In 2006 a professor and some students started to think about a new type of networking, capable of providing the communication requirements of users and applications. At the end of 2009, a vision about how to accomplish this was proposed [de Souza Pereira et al. 2009]. However, to bring this vision to life it was necessary to face several challenges. At the same time, the OpenFlow [McKeown et al. 2008] Specification version 1.0.0 was published [McKeown et al. 2009].

During 2010, we concluded that our vision of networking has a natural match with Software Defined Networking (SDN) [Greene 2009]. Since then, our research group deepened into OpenFlow and SDN. At 2011, during the II WPEIF we proposed the *Domain Title System* (DTS) [Silva et al. 2011]. At that time, the most viable way to experiment these ideas was to use Mininet [Lantz et al. 2010]. In September, 2011, a proposal to experiment the DTS at OFELIA test bed [OFELIA 2011] was selected during the MyFire Contest [MyFire 2011]. Thus it was possible to use an OpenFlow based infrastructure to go further in our research.

By using this new bridge built with Europe, the Extending and Deploying OFELIA in Brazil (EDOBRA) proposal was prepared and accepted [OFELIA 2012], then we joined the OFELIA project as partners. As a result there is currently an OFELIA Island at Uberlândia.

This work reveals the research work from a different perspective and present the learned lessons during enhancement and the use of the OFELIA experimental facility.

This paper briefly presents, at Section 2, the work conducted under the EDOBRA work package inside of the OFELIA project. Section 3 presents some concluding remarks.

2. Extending and Deploying OFELIA in Brazil (EDOBRA)

The EDOBRA work package had four challenging objectives: *i*) provide mobility control mechanisms for OpenFlow Openwrt software switches [Guimarães et al. 2013]; *ii*) extend the Entity Title Architecture (ETArch) [de Oliveira Silva et al. 2012], a clean-slate network architecture based on a OpenFlow substrate to be fully integrated with the IEEE 802.21 protocol in order to support seamless multicast and mobility [Silva et al. 2013] [Guimaraes et al. 2014]; *iii*) increase the physical extension of OFELIA by deploying a new island in Brazil and *iv*) carry out multicast and mobility experiments at OFELIA using the results of the previous objectives [Guimaraes et al. 2014].

Figure 1. Resultant OFELIA Testbed after EDOBRA Work Package

The team was composed by the Instituto de Telecomunicações (IT), from Aveiro, Portugal; the University of São Paulo (USP) and the Federal University of Uberlândia (UFU). The work package had seven different deliverables to be accomplished in one year project and three objectives where in the critical path.

In order to achieve the objectives, to handle and provide response to risks, management tools where essential during the project. Weekly meetings helped the project monitoring and control and several risk mitigation actions where executed during work package.

Another key factor to the work package was the team. Everybody was focused on the objectives and the members were always ready to help and share tasks when necessary. One previous action, revealed important in the end: before the project start, one

member from UFU spent one extra month at Aveiro and this period was important to lay the cornerstone of a strong partnership.

One challenging task was federation between the OFELIA island at UFU and UBristol, at Europe. A dedicated circuit between these institutions were created. The setup of the circuit demanded extensive communication by email and meetings between the different involved institutions (UFU, ALGAR Telecom, CPqD, RNP, AMPATH, INTERNET2 and JANET). The planning and deployment of the circuit took about four months and it was necessary to execute several tests of this connectivity considering individual network managers and specific configurations at each hop of circuit.

The deployed island at UFU enabled several experiments, as planned by the EDOBRA work package. By using the infrastructure at UFU, it was possible to conduct several tests regarding ETArch, especially the ones related with multicast and mobility, which considered novel application scenarios that were enabled by ETArch and by the exploitation of the media-independent mobile concepts in wireless environments [Guimaraes et al. 2014].

3. Concluding Remarks

Despite its challenges, the EDOBRA work package achieved its objectives and provide the planned deliveries. The software components of the DTS, i.e., the Domain Title Service Agent (DTSA) were completely re-factored and a new SDN research project was an outcome [Ferreira et al. 2014]. Besides that, new partners start a work to improve ETArch by adding QoS extensions [Silva et al. 2014] [Castillo et al. 2014]. Moreover, the solid foundation created allowed ETArch to follow the road ahead.

Management tools, weekly meetings by video conference, a team focused on the objectives and ready to help each other were some of the key success factors of the EDOBRA work package.

Collaboration between different research groups with complementary expertise is fundamental in this research area. Build strong teams in Brazil, focusing on research and experimentation will enhance the impact of our work and will allow us, as research community, be protagonist in this way towards the Future Internet.

References

- [Castillo et al. 2014] Castillo, J., Silva, F., Neto, A., Silva, F., Frosi, P., Guimaraes, C., Corujo, D., and Aguiar, R. (2014). Evolving Future Internet Clean-Slate Entity Title Architecture with Quality-Oriented Control Plane Extensions. pages 161–167.
- [de Oliveira Silva et al. 2012] de Oliveira Silva, F., Goncalves, M., de Souza Pereira, J., Pasquini, R., Rosa, P., and Kofuji, S. (2012). On the analysis of multicast traffic over the Entity Title Architecture. In *2012 18th IEEE International Conference on Networks (ICON)*, pages 30–35.
- [de Souza Pereira et al. 2009] de Souza Pereira, J., Kofuji, S., and Rosa, P. (2009). Horizontal address ontology in internet architecture. In *New Technologies, Mobility and Security (NTMS), 2009 3rd International Conference on*, pages 1–6.
- [Ferreira et al. 2014] Ferreira, C. C., Neto, N., Mota, A., Silva, F. d. O., Pereira, J. H. d. S., Neto, A., Corujo, D., Guimaraes, C., Rosa, P. F., Kofuji, S. T., and Aguiar, R.

- (2014). Towards a Carrier Grade SDN Controller: Integrating OpenFlow with Telecom Services. In *The Tenth Advanced International Conference on Telecommunications (AICT)*, Paris. IARIA.
- [Greene 2009] Greene, K. (2009). TR10: Software-Defined networking. *MIT Technology Review*, 112(2).
- [Guimaraes et al. 2014] Guimaraes, C., Corujo, D., Silva, F. d. O., Rosa, P. F., Venâncio Neto, A. J., and Aguiar, R. L. (2014). IEEE 802.21-enabled Entity Title Architecture for Handover Optimization. In *2014 IEEE Wireless and Communications and Networking Conference*, Piscataway, NJ.: IEEE.
- [Guimarães et al. 2013] Guimarães, C., Corujo, D., Aguiar, R. L., Silva, F. d. O., and Rosa, P. (2013). Empowering Software Defined Wireless Networks Through Media Independent Handover Management. In *Globecom 2013 - Next Generation Networking Symposium (GC13 NGN)*, Atlanta, USA.
- [Lantz et al. 2010] Lantz, B., Heller, B., and McKeown, N. (2010). A network in a laptop: rapid prototyping for software-defined networks. *Proceedings of the Ninth ACM SIGCOMM Workshop on Hot Topics in Networks*, page 19:1–19:6. ACM ID: 1868466.
- [McKeown et al. 2008] McKeown, N., Anderson, T., Balakrishnan, H., Parulkar, G., Peterson, L., Rexford, J., Shenker, S., and Turner, J. (2008). OpenFlow: enabling innovation in campus networks. *SIGCOMM Comput. Commun. Rev.*, 38(2):69–74. ACM ID: 1355746.
- [McKeown et al. 2009] McKeown, N., Pfaff, B., Heller, B., Talayco, D., Erickson, D., Gibb, G., Appenzeller, G., Tourrilhes, J., Pettit, J., Yap, K., Casado, M., Kobayashi, M., Balland, P., Price, R., Sherwood, R., and Yiakoumis, Y. (2009). OpenFlow Switch Specification. Version 1.0.0.
- [MyFire 2011] MyFire (2011). MyFire Contest. <http://www.my-fire.eu/contest>.
- [OFELIA 2011] OFELIA (2011). OpenFlow in europe - linking infrastructure and applications. <http://www.fp7-ofelia.eu/about-ofelia/>.
- [OFELIA 2012] OFELIA (2012). OFELIA second open call for OpenFlow experiments success and new partners. <http://www.fp7-ofelia.eu/news-and-events/press-releases/ofelia-2nd-open-call-success/>.
- [Silva et al. 2013] Silva, F. d. O., Corujo, D., Guimarães, C., Pereira, J. H. d. S., Rosa, P. F. R., Kofuji, S. T., and Aguiar, R. (2013). Enabling Network Mobility by Using IEEE 802.21 Integrated with the Entity Title Architecture. In *Anais do IV Workshop de Pesquisa Experimental na Internet do Futuro (WPEIF)*, pages 29–34, Brasília. Sociedade Brasileira de Computação.
- [Silva et al. 2011] Silva, F. d. O., Pereira, J. H. d. S., Kofuji, S. T., and Rosa, P. F. (2011). Domain title service for future internet networks. In *Anais do II Workshop de Pesquisa Experimental na Internet do Futuro (WPEIF)*, Campo Grande. SBC.
- [Silva et al. 2014] Silva, F. S. D. d., Lema, J. C., Neto, A. J., Silva, F. d. O., Rosa, P. F., Corujo, D., Guimaraes, C., and Aguiar, R. (2014). Entity Title Architecture Extensions Towards Advanced Quality-oriented Mobility Control Capabilities. In *19th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (IEEE ISCC 2014)*, Madeira, Portugal.